

CODEN [USA]: IAJ PBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**STUDY TO DETERMINE THE VARIOUS CAUSES OF CHEST
PAIN IN CHILDREN**¹Dr Alia Khanum, ²Dr Bismillah Noor, ³Dr Sania Nasrullah
^{1,2,3} Nishter Hospital Multan**Article Received:** March 2020**Accepted:** April 2020**Published:** May 2020**Abstract:*****Aim:** The aim of the study is to determine the various causes of chest pain in children.****Study Design:** A prospective study.****Place and Duration:** In the Pediatric Medicine Unit II of Jinnah Hospital Lahore for one-year duration from March 2019 to March 2020.****Methods:** Thirty-five children with a primary complaint of chest pain were prospectively studied. The average age was 9.7 years for boys and 8.9 years for girls; 60% were male.****Results:** The most frequently diagnosed cause was psychogenic (54.2%). Forty percent of the patients were classified as having idiopathic chest pain. Precordial pain was encountered in 2.9%, along with costochondritis and mitral valve prolapse.****Conclusion:** It is concluded that chest pain in children is a relatively benign symptom which is infrequently associated with a serious underlying organic condition; extensive laboratory investigations are not required. Psychogenic chest pain is a prevalent problem that commonly causes considerable anxiety in children and their families.***Corresponding author:****Dr. Alia Khanum,**

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Please cite this article in press Alia Khanum et al, *Study To Determine The Various Causes Of Chest Pain In Children.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(05).

INTRODUCTION:

Chest pain is a relatively common presenting problem in children. Nevertheless, it has received inadequate attention in pediatric journals and standard textbooks.

In other texts, contradictory discussions regarding etiology and evaluation of the disease are presented which may result in different approaches to the management of the condition. The purpose of this paper is to present the clinical features and underlying causes of a prospective study of children who were referred to the pediatric cardiac clinic complaining of chest pain.

PATIENTS AND METHODS:

This study was held in the Pediatric Medicine Unit II of Jinnah Hospital Lahore for one-year duration from March 2019 to March 2020. Children with the primary complaint of chest were included in this prospective

study. Thirty-five cases were recognized during a 2-year period ending on July 30, 1985.

Complete history and physical examination were carried out in all patients. Cardiac auscultation was performed while the patients were in supine, sitting and erect positions. Since laboratory evaluation in previous studies had revealed infrequent abnormalities, in this study the paramedical investigations were selectively performed whenever it was deemed appropriate.

RESULTS:

There were 21 boys and 14 girls. the average age of the boys was 9.7 years (range, 3-15 years) and that of the girls was 8.9 years (range, 4-13 years).

The frequency of the etiological factors is shown in Table I.

Table I. Etiology of chest pain

	Patients	
	Number	Percent
Idiopathic	14	40.0%
Psychogenic	19	54.3%
Costochondritis	1	2.9%
Mitral valve prolapses	1	2.9%
Total	35	100.0%

In 14 patients (40%) no cause for chest pain was identified. Psychiatric evaluation revealed some psychogenic abnormalities in more than half of the patients, to which chest pain could be attributed; only 2 patients (5.8%) had true organic disease.

Since the psychogenic group has formed the majority of the children presenting with chest pain, more detailed information which could have precipitated precordial pain is listed in Table II.

Table II. Psychogenic factors precipitating chest pain

Age	Sex	Situations
12	M	Asthmatic, Nervousness, School exam, Heart disease in family
9	F	Heart disease in family, Overanxious mother, New school
8	M	New baby in family
12	F	Obesity; teased by other children
8	F	Overanxious mother
12	M	Anxiety due to school exam
12	M	Obesity; teased by other children
11	M	Headache and extremity pain
7	M	Overprotected child
11	M	Hyperventilation
10	F	Nervousness
7	F	New baby in family
8	F	Overprotected child, Father has chest pain
11	F	Nervousness, Aunt has mitral stenosis
9	F	Nervousness, Death of father, Grandfather has heart disease
11	M	Nervousness, Father died of myocardial infarction 3 months earlier
11	F	Abdominal and extremity pain
10	M	Dizziness. Nervousness
15	M	Nervousness

The duration of chest pain varied from 2 weeks to 2 years. Eighty percent of the children with idiopathic chest pain and 36% of the patients with psychogenic precordial pain had symptoms for more than 6 months. The shortest duration of complaint belonged to

children with costochondritis and mitral valve prolapse. The nature of pain (Table III) did not help to differentiate the diagnostic categorization, nor was it useful in the etiological classification. The symptom meant "heart" to all of the children.

Table III. Nature of the chest pain

Description of Pain	Patients	
	Number	Percent
Dull pressure	31	88.6%
Sharp like a needle	1	2.9%
"Pouring blood"	1	2.9%
Blow by a fist	1	2.9%
"Wind-like" feeling	1	2.9%
Total	35	100.0%

The age, sex, and socio-economic status of the study group were compared with the characteristics of the 100 randomly selected records of the clinic population. The age and sex distribution of the study and control groups were found to be similar: in the study group the mean age was 9 years and 60% were male, while in the control population, 58% were male and the average age was 10 years. In the control population, the socioeconomic status, based on the father's occupation was rated good (60%), fair (30%), or poor (10%), while in the study group 63% were rated good and 37% fair; with no patient of poor socio-economic status. Laboratory investigations such as complete blood count, erythrocyte sedimentation rate,

SGOT, and urinalysis were carried out in 5 children with normal results. Chest x-ray and electrocardiography were performed in 12 patients. Chest radiography was negative in all except one child with left cost sternal chondritis. The ECGs were normal in all except one, which showed some left ventricular preponderance. Echocardiography was performed in one case who had a non-ejection click on physical examination, and proved to have mitral valve prolapse.

DISCUSSION:

Although chest pain commonly denotes serious underlying disease in adults, it is believed to be a

benign pediatric problem. Furthermore, chest pain in children rarely signals an organic cause or a serious underlying disease that is not apparent from a complete history and physical examination. Although Coleman presented a comprehensive review of organic etiologies of chest pain in children, others, as well as the present study, found that the majority of children with precordial pain did not have an identifiable cause, and a sizable number have some form of psychogenic factor. The major concern of the patients and their families was the belief that the chest pain means heart disease, as the symptoms meant "heart" to all of our patients. Nevertheless, in only one child in the present study (with mitral valve prolapse) and very infrequently in other studies was heart disease diagnosed.

In the present study, the majority of the children were diagnosed as having psychogenic chest pain following some forms of emotional conflict. The distress produced by a socio-environmental crisis, the household atmosphere, and relationships of the child with his parents and peers are some of the important factors leading to psychogenic chest pain in our patients. Psychogenic chest pain seems to be more prevalent in girls as has been reported by Asnes and associates but our study as well as that of Driscoll and colleagues did not substantiate this belief: both sexes were almost evenly distributed in the two latter studies. Chest pain in children with costochondritis is readily recognized by the presence of tenderness and swelling of the rib cartilage. There was one child in this study with left cost sternal chondritis which might represent an example of Tietze's syndrome. The natural course of this syndrome is usually benign. Its epidemiology and etiology are not known. The incidence of costochondritis in other reports was higher than this study, but the reason for such a discrepancy is not clear. Chest pain was encountered infrequently in mitral valve prolapse, as evidenced by finding of only one patient in our group and rarely in other reports. The cause of chest pain in this disease is unclear. A thorough physical examination and the finding of a late systolic murmur and/or mid-systolic click is highly suggestive of the condition.

The duration of chest pain tended to be longer in idiopathic and psychogenic types than in children with an organic cause of symptom. It is interesting that chest pain was not found in children belonging to the low socio-economic group. It is possible that the family structure, the overprotective attitude of the parents, and the child's affect in fair to good socio-economic classes played some roles. Since the results of this study and those of others demonstrate that the

laboratory investigations do not yield helpful diagnostic information, it is recommended that extensive paramedical work-up in evaluating a child with uncomplicated chest pain be avoided.

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